

**TIL, TA'LIM, TARJIMA
ЯЗЫК, ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ, ПЕРЕВОД
LANGUAGE, EDUCATION, TRANSLATION**

TA'LIM

Khudayberdiyeva Malikaxon Ergashali qizi

Teacher, Department of English
Gulistan State University
Gulistan City, Uzbekistan

**INTRODUCING STORIES INTO EFL CLASSROOM: BENEFITS FOR
BASIC LANGUAGE SKILLS**

ABSTRACT

The notion that the main objective of EFL teaching is to help students to communicate fluently in the target language cause most teachers still believe that an EFL class should focus on mastering linguistic elements only. However, recent trend in EFL teaching indicates the necessity of integrating literature because its rich potential to provide an authentic model of language use. Among literary genres, short stories seem to be the most suitable choice for this due to its potential to help students enhance the four skills – listening, speaking, reading and writing – more effectively because of the motivational benefit embedded in the stories. The purpose of this article is to familiarize EFL instructors with the effectiveness of using short stories in EFL instruction. After presenting criteria for selecting a short story, discussions are focused on how to exploit a short story for enhancing students' language skills.

Keywords: EFL, classroom, story, benefits, language skills, motivation.

Xudayberdiyeva Malikaxon Ergashali qizi

O'qituvchi, "Ingliz tili va adabiyoti" kafedrası
Guliston davlat universiteti
Guliston sh., O'zbekiston

**EFL DARS JARAYONIGA HIKOYALARNI KIRITISH: ASOSIY TIL
KO'NIKMALARI UCHUN AFZALLIKLAR**

ANNOTATSIYA

Ingliz tilini xorijiy til sifatida (ITXTL) o'qitishning asosiy maqsadi talabalarga maqsadli tilda ravon muloqot qilishda yordam berishdir, lekin ko'pchilik o'qituvchilar hali ham ITXTL sinfida faqat lingvistik elementlarni o'zlashtirishga e'tibor qaratish kerak, deb hisoblashadi. Biroq, ingliz tilini o'qitishdagi so'nggi tendentsiya adabiyotni integratsiyalash zarurligini ko'rsatadi, chunki uning boy imkoniyatlari tildan foydalanishning haqiqiy modelini ta'minlaydi. Adabiy janrlar orasida qisqa hikoyalar o'quvchilarning to'rtta ko'nikmalarini – tinglash, gapirish, o'qish va yozishni – hikoyalarga kiritilgan motivatsion foyda tufayli samaraliroq oshirishga yordam berish potentsiali tufayli buning uchun eng mos variant bo'lib tuyuladi. Ushbu maqolaning maqsadi ITXTL o'qituvchilarini ingliz tilini o'qitishda qisqa hikoyalardan foydalanish samaradorligi bilan tanishtirishdir. Qisqa hikoyani tanlash mezonlarini taqdim etgandan so'ng, muhokamalar talabalarining til ko'nikmalarini oshirish uchun qisqa hikoyadan qanday foydalanishga qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ITXTL, dars jarayoni, hikoya, afzalliklar, til ko'nikmalari, motivatsiya.

Худайбердиева Маликахон Эргашали кизи

Преподаватель, кафедра английского языка и литературы

Гулистанский государственный университет

г. Гулистан, Узбекистан

ВНЕДРЕНИЕ РАССКАЗА В ПРОЦЕСС ОБУЧЕНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ КАК ИНОСТРАННОМУ (АЯИ): ПРЕИМУЩЕСТВА ДЛЯ БАЗОВЫХ ЯЗЫКОВЫХ НАВЫКОВ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Представление о том, что основная цель преподавания английского языка как иностранного (АЯИ) языка состоит в том, чтобы помочь учащимся свободно общаться на изучаемом языке, приводит к тому, что большинство учителей по-прежнему считают, что урок английского языка должен быть сосредоточен только на освоении языковых элементов. Тем не менее, недавняя тенденция в обучении английскому языку указывает на необходимость интеграции литературы, поскольку она обладает богатым потенциалом для предоставления аутентичной модели использования языка. Среди литературных жанров короткие рассказы кажутся наиболее подходящим выбором для этого из-за их потенциала помочь учащимся более эффективно развивать четыре навыка — аудирование, говорение, чтение и письмо — из-за мотивационной пользы, заложенной в рассказах. Цель этой статьи — ознакомить преподавателей АЯИ с эффективностью использования коротких рассказов в обучении АЯИ. После представления критериев для выбора

рассказа обсуждаются способы использования рассказа для улучшения языковых навыков учащихся.

Ключевые слова: АЯИ, процесс обучения, рассказ, преимущества, языковые навыки, мотивация.

Introduction. In the nineteenth century, the Grammar Translation Method predominated ESL/EFL teaching. In that era, translating literary texts from the second/foreign language to the students' native language was one of the main learning activities. But when this method was replaced by the Structuralism Approach, during the 1960s to the end of 1970s, literature was no longer used. Structuralism Approach was concerned with correctness of grammatical form and not with content, interpretation of the written word or style. In other words, teaching a foreign language was regarded as a matter of linguistics. Then, when the Direct Method, the Audiolingual Method, Community Language Learning, Suggestopedia, the Silent Way, Total Physical Response, and the Natural Approach successively dominated ESL/EFL teaching, literature was not utilized [1]. Later on and with the appearance of the Communicative Approach in the late 70`s and very early 80`s, literature was also ignored. The tendency in the EFL classrooms was to teach "usable, practical" contents [7, 13]. Thus, literary works had no place in the curriculum. During this period most EFL courses were mainly aimed to enable the students to communicate orally. Consequently, dialogues dominated the curriculum.

However, since the 1980s the situation changed quite radically and literature is undergoing an extensive reconsideration within the language teaching profession. The inclusion of literary works in ESL/EFL classes has attracted more interest among teachers, and more and more studies on how to use literature in EFL/ESL classes are conducted. This interest in using literature in language teaching lies in three interrelated elements: authenticity, culture and personal growth. First of all, literary texts can be more beneficial than informational materials in stimulating the acquisition process as they provide authentic contexts for processing new language. Since literary texts contain language intended for native speakers, literature stands as a model for language learners to become familiar with different forms and conventions [3, 4; 19]. Containing real examples of grammatical structures and vocabulary items, the literary texts raise learners' awareness of the range of the target language and advance their competence in all language skills [13]. Second, using literature in language teaching has the advantage of providing cultural information about the target language. Literary texts increase foreign language learners' insight into the country and the people whose language is being learnt [3], which fosters learners' ability to interpret discourse in different social and cultural target language contexts [16]. Finally, since literature enables students to understand and appreciate other cultures, societies and ideologies different from their own, it encourages personal growth and intellectual development [2, 2-4].

In line with these ideas, Littlewood [8, 179] emphasizes the importance of the use of literature in EFL classes by showing the fact that a major problem of language teaching in the classroom is the creation of an authentic situation for language. All language classrooms, especially those outside the community of native speakers, are isolated from the context of events and situations which produce natural language. Literature can overcome this problem because, in literary works, language creates its own context. The actual situation of the reader becomes immaterial as he or she looks on the events created by language. These events create, in turn, a context of situation for the language of the book and enable it to transcend the artificial classroom situation. In short, literary works undoubtedly enable students to understand the language better by providing the students with real world experiences, relationships between society and people where the target language is spoken, even if they are fictions.

Problem and Methodology. Despite its benefits for students, some objections are always raised against the use of literature in public schools due to overcrowded classes, overloaded syllabus and limited time – some problems commonly met in elementary to high public schools in almost all developing countries. First, the deviated and figurative language of poetry necessitates very long time to grasp. Second, the length of novel will make it difficult for such classes to finish. Finally, drama can be used in classes, but it will be difficult to act out a play in crowded classes within limited course hours. Considering these objections, it is obvious that among literary forms, short-story which is defined by Poe [1, 158] “as a narrative that can be read at one sitting of from one-half hour to two hours, and that is limited to ‘a certain unique or single effect,’ to which every detail is subordinate” seems to be the most suitable one to use in public schools. Since it is short, and aims at giving a ‘single effect’, there is usually one plot, a few characters; there is no detailed description of setting. So, it is easy for the students to follow the story line of the work [9, 22].

This reason, that short stories are the most suitable literary genre to use in English teaching due to its shortness, is supported by Collie and Slater [3, 196] when they list four advantages of using short stories for language teachers. First, short stories are practical as their length is long enough to cover entirely in one or two class sessions. Second, short stories are not complicated for students to work with on their own. Third, short stories have a variety of choice for different interests and tastes. Finally, short stories can be used with all levels (beginner to advance), all ages (young learners to adults) and all classes. Pardede’s study revealed that the majority of English teachers training students basically found short stories interesting to use both as materials for self-enjoyment and of as components language skill classes. The findings denoted that only 0.37% of the responses went into “Disagree” criterion; and 18.4%, “Neutral”. The other 81.5% went into the criteria of “Agree” and “Strongly Agree” [12].

Choosing the Text. The use of short-story in English teaching should be aimed to encourage the students to use what they have previously learnt. By doing this, the learning process will be student-centered. However, the teacher plays a great role. She/he must choose a suitable text to use in class, and should help her/his students understand the story with various activities [15, 71].

In using short stories to teach English, story selection is indeed one of the most important roles of the teacher. Since the lengths of short-stories quite vary, choose a story short enough to handle within course hours. The shortness of the text is important for the students because they will see that they can read, understand and finish something in English, and it will give the students a feeling of achievement and self-confidence. Besides the length of the text, Hill [5, 15] points out three other basic criteria of choosing the text: (1) the needs and abilities of the students; (2) the linguistic and stylistic level of the text; (3) the amount of background information required for a true appreciation of the material.

The importance of considering these criteria could be perceived by realizing that the vocabulary and sentence structure of the short-story to be studied must be suitable to the level of the students. The short-stories with archaic, slang, foreign words, and allusions, having sentences imitating the speech of a particular locality or ignorant people or foreigners should be avoided if the text is intended for students below intermediate level. Similarly, very long sentences are difficult for students to understand. As students will not understand these sentences and words, they will get bored and not read the work. Therefore, before giving the short-story, the teacher should decide the readability of the text.

In order to meet that readability criterion, using graded or simplified stories is possibly the most practical way. According to Ur [19, 150], "... the use of 'authentic' text with less proficient learners is often frustrating and counter-productive". Therefore, the use of simplified text with less proficient readers is highly suggested for the sake of suiting the texts with the level of students.

In addition to the previous criteria, Spack suggests the aspect of interest to be considered [18]. According to him, it is important for the teacher to choose stories that would interest students that he/she most likes to read and teach, and that have been made into film to provide visual interpretation. McKay [10, 322] and Rivers [14, 230] point out that students read and enjoy a text if the subject-matter of the text is relevant to their life experience and interests.

Short Stories and Language Skills Development. Short stories allow teachers to teach the four skills to all levels of language proficiency. Guskey [4, 53] indicates that "short stories can, if selected and exploited appropriately, provide quality text content which will greatly enhance ELT courses for learners at intermediate levels of proficiency". According to him, short stories could be very beneficial materials in ELT reinforcement by using them in learning activities such as, discussion, writing and acting out dialogues.

A. Reading

Short stories are very useful in the trials to improve students' vocabulary and reading. The results of Lao and Krashen's [6] study which compared the reading achievement between a group of students that read literary texts and a second group that read non-literary texts at a university in Hong Kong revealed that the group who read literary texts made better improvement in vocabulary and reading.

B. Writing

Short story can be a powerful and motivating source for writing in ESL/EFL, both as a model and as subject matter. Short story as a model occurs when students' writing becomes closely similar to the original work or clearly imitates its content, theme, organization, and /or style. However, when student writing exhibits original thinking like interpretation or analysis, or when it emerges from, or is creatively stimulated by, the reading, literature serves as subject matter. In accordance with this, Oster [11, 85] affirms that literature helps students to write more creatively. Teachers can create a variety of writing activities to help students to develop their writing skills. They can ask students to write dialogues or more complex writing activities if students have reached a high level of language proficiency.

C. Speaking and Listening

Short story can also be a powerful and motivating source for teaching both speaking and listening [17, 10]. Oral reading, dramatization, improvisation, role-playing, reenactment, and discussion are some effective learning activities which center on a short story EFL classes can use for enhancing these two skills. Asking students to read story aloud can develop their speaking as well as listening skills. Moreover, it also leads to improving pronunciation.

Conclusion. Since the objective of EFL teaching is to help students to communicate fluently in the target language, teachers should provide an authentic model of language use. To do it, she/he should focus not only on linguistic but also on literary and cultural elements. Since short stories offer these elements, they are highly beneficial to use in ESL/EFL teaching programs. However, the selection of short stories should be done in reference to the course objective, the learners' profile, and the story content in order to make the best of it. Since every teaching situation is unique, the use of one single piece of literature varies from classroom to classroom and from teacher to teacher. Like what the discussion in this paper shows, short stories can be used to provide different activities for reading, listening, writing and speaking classes. Short story creates a meaningful context to teach different language focuses and to improve the students' interpretative strategies. Last but not least, the same story may also serve for some other language focuses or skills such as vocabulary development.

Иқтибослар/Сноски/References

1. Abrams, M. H. A Glossary of Literary Term. 11th edition. – New York: Rinehart, 2020.

2. Carter, R., Long, M. N. Teaching literature. – Harlow: Longman, 2011.
3. Collie, J., Slater, S. Literature in the Language Classroom. 7th edition. – Glasgow: Cambridge University Press, 2021.
4. Guskey, T. R. Lessons of Mastery Learning // Educational Leadership. – 2019. – Vol. 68 (2). – P. 53-57.
5. Hill, J. Using Literature in Language Teaching. 3rd edition. – London: Macmillan, 2014.
6. Lao, C.Y., Krashen, S. The impact of popular literature study on literacy development in EFL: More evidence for the power of reading // System. – 2000. Vol. 28. – P. 261-270
7. Lazar, G. Literature and Language Teaching. 2nd edition. – Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2013.
8. Littlewood, W. “Literature in the School Foreign-Language Course”. In C. J. Brumfit & R. A. Carter (Eds.), Literature and Language Teaching. – Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2000.
9. McKay, S. L. Literature in the ESL classroom. – London: Oxford University Press, 2016.
10. McKay, S. L. Literature as Content for ESL/EFL. – London: Oxford University Press, 2011.
11. Oster, J. Seeing with Different Eyes: Another View of Literature in the ESL Class // TESOL Quarterly, - 2019. – Vol. 23. – P. 85-103
12. Pardede, P. Short Stories Use in Language Skills Classes: Students’ Interest and Perception. In N. T. Zacharias & C. Manara (Eds.) Bringing Literature and Linguistics into EFL Classrooms: Insights from Research and Classroom Practice (pp. 101-108). – Newcastle: Cambridge Scholars Publishing, 2011.
13. Povey, J. F. Literature in TESOL Programs: The Language and the Culture // TESOL Quarterly. – 2017. – Vol. 1. – P. 40-46.
14. Rivers, W. M. Teaching Foreign-Language Skills. 5th edition. – Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2011.
15. Rose, D. H., Myer, A. Teaching Every Student in the Digital Age: Universal Design for Learning. – Alexandria: AS & CD, 2012.
16. Savvidou, C. An Integrated Approach to the Teaching of Literature in the EFL Classroom // The Internet TESL Journal. – 2014. – Vol. 10 (12). URL: http://iteslj.org/Techniques/Savvidou_Literature.html
17. Sell, R. D. Why is Literature Central? // Review of English Language Teaching. – 2015. – Vol. 5 (1). –P. 4-19.
18. Spack, R. Literature, Reading, Writing, and ESL: Bridging the Gaps // TESOL Quarterly. – 2015. – Vol. 19. – P. 703-725.
19. Ur, P. A Course in Language Teaching: Practice and Theory. – Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1996.